

Master in Sound and Music Computing
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Sounds of Rest: Using Auditory Stimuli to Optimize Daytime Naps

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Abstract

Sleep is a fundamental yet enigmatic biological process essential for maintaining overall health and well-being. Despite its importance, the precise mechanisms and functions of sleep remain only partially understood. This thesis explores the potential for sound to enhance sleep quality during short daytime naps, a practice increasingly recognized for its health benefits. The study specifically examines the effectiveness of different variations of broadband noise in improving sleep quality.

The research is motivated by the need for non-pharmacological interventions to address common sleep issues, which can lead to significant health problems. The primary objective is to design, develop, and evaluate auditory stimuli tailored to the N1 and N2 stages of NREM. The methodology involves collecting EEG data from participants during short naps, delivering different auditory based on their current sleep stage, and assessing their impact on sleep quality through both subjective and objective measures.

Overall, the results of this study suggest encouraging yet statistically insignificant trends in sleep quality across subjective and objective measures. The data collected provide a foundation for understanding the relationship between sound and sleep, contributing to the ongoing research in this area.

Keywords: EEG; Nap; NREM; N1; N2; Sleep spindle

List of Abbreviations

AASM - American Academy of Sleep Medicine

CSV - Comma Separated Values

ECG - Electrocardiography

EEG - Electroencephalography

EMG - Electromyography

EOG - Electrooculography

fMRI - Functional Magnetic Resonance Imaging

LAMF - Low-Amplitude Mixed-Frequency

M - Mean

N1 - NREM Stage 1

N2 - NREM Stage 2

N3 - NREM Stage 3

NREM - Non-Rapid Eye Movement

PLM - Periodic Limb Movements

PPG - Photoplethysmography

PSG - Polysomnography

PSQI - Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index

PVT - Psychomotor Vigilance Test

REM - Rapid Eye Movement

RMS - Root Mean Square

SD - Standard Deviation

SE - Sleep Efficiency

SO - Slow Oscillations

SOL - Sleep Onset Latency

dB SPL - Decibels Sound Pressure Level

SWS - Slow Wave Sleep

SCN - Suprachiasmatic Nucleus

TST - Total Sleep Time

TWT - Total Wake Time

W - Kendall's Coefficient of Concordance

WASO - Wake After Sleep Onset

WHO - World Health Organization

YASA - Yet Another Spindle Algorithm

Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Background

Sleep is a fundamental aspect of human life, deeply woven into our biological rhythms, and essential for overall health and well-being. Each night, nearly every human undergoes this important yet under-explored change in consciousness. Hours are spent departing from waking life, yet we are left with little to no memory of our experience of this upon awakening. While forming a precise definition of the complex processes involved in human sleep is not yet feasible, to advance our understanding scientists have identified sleep as an easily reversible period of reduced activity associated with metabolic and neural processes, and physical behaviors in humans, such as laying down with the eyes closed. The American Academy of Sleep Medicine (AASM) recommends 7-9 hours of sleep per night to maintain a healthy lifestyle [1]. To align with this recommendation, modern societies have adapted to facilitate one extended sleep period at night, which is both beneficial and convenient. Insufficient or poor-quality sleep can contribute significantly to the development of both acute and chronic health disorders [2].

Despite its importance, it may not be easy or possible to get the recommended amount of sleep per night due to sleep disruption from external and internal stimuli, or several physical and mental disorders. Daytime napping can be an effective way

to decrease the negative effects of nighttime sleep deprivation. Short periods of sleep during the day can provide similar benefits to nighttime sleep without disrupting daily activities. However, daytime naps present a different set of challenges: napping for too little time may prevent one from accessing the benefits of sleep, while napping for too long poses the risk of entering deep stages of sleep that can leave the napper feeling more exhausted than when they first fell asleep. This phenomenon is commonly referred to as sleep inertia [3].

According to the National Sleep Foundation¹, the ideal nap lasts between 10-20 minutes or 90 minutes. A 10-20-minute nap allows the emergence of sleep benefits without reaching deep enough sleep to cause sleep inertia. Importantly, humans do not reach progressively deeper levels of sleep with increased nap length. Instead, most humans sleep and awaken in cycles of about 90 minutes, thus a nap of 90 minutes allows the napper to enter and emerge from the deepest level of sleep and reawaken having reached a lighter stage at the end of a cycle. In most modern cultures, finding enough time during the workweek to take a 90-minute nap may be a challenge in itself, which is likely a reason that shorter naps have become increasingly popular.

Short daytime naps, or "power naps", are an accepted practice throughout cultures worldwide. Their ability to boost energy, motivation, focus, and memory without disrupting the quality of nighttime sleep makes them a valuable tool for enhancing productivity and mood. One of the main challenges of power naps is reducing the amount of time taken to fall asleep, commonly referred to as sleep onset latency, and maximizing sleep quality given the limited time frame. As such, exploring methods to optimize these short sleep periods is of significant interest in both personal and professional settings.

Many individuals employ sound as a tool for sleep optimization. Various types of broadband noise, containing all frequencies of sound that humans can hear, are used to create an auditory environment conducive to falling asleep quickly and maintaining stable sleep. In addition to noise, some individuals prefer soothing music or

¹<https://www.sleepfoundation.org/napping>

natural soundscapes, such as rainfall or ocean waves, to further promote relaxation. These auditory interventions are readily accessible through mobile applications and specialized devices.

To support sleep enhancement efforts in personal settings, at-home sleep monitoring technology has become increasingly popular. Devices such as wearable fitness trackers, smartwatches, and dedicated sleep monitors provide valuable insights into sleep patterns, duration, and quality. These technologies help users identify sleep disruptions, track sleep cycles, and understand how factors like exercise, diet, and stress impact their sleep. By providing personalized feedback and recommendations, these tools can assist individuals in making adjustments to their habits and environment to improve overall sleep quality.

1.2 Motivation

The motivation behind this thesis originates from my personal experiences with sleep loss as well as the increase in at-home sleep technology. In recent years, multiple close family members of mine have faced varying levels of difficulty falling or staying asleep. I have witnessed frustration and distress when exploring non-medical sleep interventions only to be met with another unsuccessful solution. All of my family members who have faced this issue have tried their best to avoid medical interventions due to their high costs and potential for undesirable side effects. With advances in sleep health technology, new interventions are becoming accessible to the general public every day. Currently, several non-invasive sleep monitoring devices, such as watches and rings², are popular choices. These devices, however, typically provide insights only after waking up. Brainwave monitoring technology has historically been out of reach for everyday users due to its price and difficulty to operate. However, many brain-monitoring headbands³ have been made publicly available. Given that many people have access to some form of sound generation (such as a phone speaker), I was motivated to understand how sound-based sleep

²ouraring.com

³<https://www.science.org/content/article/brain-monitoring-headbands-could-track-your-sleep-well-sleep-lab>

interventions could be improved with the integration of real-time sleep monitoring technology.

1.3 Study Overview

This thesis builds on the work of James W. Antony and Ken A. Paller, whose 2017 study [4] examined the influence of non-musical broadband noise on brainwave patterns during both daytime naps and overnight sleep. While their research primarily focused on the effects of such noise over extended sleep periods, this thesis aims to explore whether similar effects occur during short naps. Additional insights are drawn from a literature review [5] that analyzed studies on the impact of broadband noise on sleep, suggesting that this type of noise could improve sleep quality by masking disruptive environmental sounds. However, the review did not consider the effects of broadband noise in environments where external sounds are controlled.

To address this gap, the current study investigates how different types of auditory stimuli, particularly pink noise, affect the time it takes to fall asleep and the overall quality of sleep during short naps. Pink noise, with its balanced frequency spectrum, has been suggested to aid in faster sleep onset and improved sleep quality. The study also explores whether modulated pink noise, which varies in intensity, might enhance specific sleep stages essential for memory consolidation. By focusing on naps taken without external noise disturbances, this research seeks to deepen our understanding of the relationship between auditory stimuli and sleep quality during brief sleep periods.

1.4 Objectives

The objectives of this thesis are multi-faceted:

Explore possible enhancements of sleep efficiency using sound: By identifying auditory stimuli that help to reduce the amount of time taken to fall asleep and enhance the quality of sleep throughout the nap, this thesis aims to contribute

to the body of knowledge by providing support for an evidence-based strategy to improve daytime nap efficiency. This would be particularly relevant for individuals who wouldn't otherwise have time in the middle of the day to rest.

Shed light on the improvement of cognitive and emotional well-being:

By improving the overall quality of naps, this thesis aims to provide a method to strengthen the associated positive effects, such as memory, attention, and decision-making, as well as emotional regulation. Improvements to cognitive processes used daily may contribute to overall improvements in productivity and well-being, especially in high-stress environments.

Demonstrate accessibility and practicality of sound interventions:

This thesis aims to contribute to the body of knowledge supporting the use of sound as a non-invasive, easily accessible, and cost-effective tool to improve nap quality. Pink noise can be easily generated using simple methods, often requiring only a basic speaker, making it an appealing solution for individuals who may wish to avoid pharmaceutical interventions due to high costs and potential side effects, or the complexity of behavioral modifications designed to improve sleep.

Chapter 2

State of the Art

Understanding the relationship between sound and sleep has become a focal point of research aimed at enhancing sleep quality and overall well-being. While music has been recognized for its potential to facilitate sleep onset and continuity, recent studies have extended this exploration to encompass non-musical auditory interventions [6]. Investigations into continuous noise, particularly white noise, have revealed its efficacy in promoting sleep onset and maintenance across various populations [5]. Moreover, emerging research explores stage-specific sleep enhancement, shedding light on the nuanced effects of auditory interventions on different sleep stages, from onset to deep sleep. As researchers better understand the mechanisms behind these interventions, methodologies for monitoring sleep stages and integrating sound for sleep enhancement are evolving. From traditional clinical methods to innovative technologies like automatic sleep scoring systems, the landscape of sleep research is expanding, offering new insights and possibilities for tailored interventions. This chapter explores the methodologies and technologies employed in sleep monitoring as well as the design considerations essential for implementing effective sound-based interventions tailored to individual sleep patterns. Through a synthesis of research findings and technological advancements, this chapter navigates the complex terrain of sound and sleep integration, offering a comprehensive overview of the state of the art in this burgeoning field.

2.1 Sleep

Sleep is a necessary biological process that occurs to some extent in every animal species, holding an important role in regulating many physiological and behavioral functions. Although sleep varies in its precise features among different animals, it is generally recognized as a reversible behavioral state characterized by a disconnection from and lack of responsiveness to the environment [7]. In mammalian sleep physiological characteristics such as reduced body movement and electromyographic activity, reduced responsiveness to external stimuli, closed eyes, reduced breathing rates, altered body position and brain wave architecture may be observed. Polysomnography (PSG), a comprehensive recording of the biophysiological changes that occur during sleep, is commonly used to measure these parameters, providing insights into the nature and quality of sleep [8]. The definition of mammalian sleep is based on the interplay between activity, metabolism, and the electrical brain signals captured in the electroencephalogram (EEG).

Sleep researchers acknowledge its role in numerous physiological processes. Primarily, it plays a critical role in brain function, aiding in memory consolidation, learning, and cognitive processing by allowing the brain to clear out toxins accumulated during waking hours. Sleep is also crucial for physical health, as it promotes tissue growth and repair, strengthens the immune system, and regulates hormones involved in growth, appetite, and stress. Furthermore, it helps maintain emotional stability by processing emotions and reducing anxiety, contributing to better mood regulation [9, 10].

Normal human sleep consists of two physiologically distinct states: rapid eye movement (REM) and non-rapid eye movement (NREM). Throughout a typical night of sleep, the brain shifts cyclically between NREM and REM sleep with cycles lasting 90 minutes on average, as shown in **Figure 1** [7, 11]. Variations in both the overall cycle length as well as the distribution of time spent in each stage can occur based on age, ambient temperature, medications and drugs, and sleep disorders [7].

Figure 1: A graphical representation of a typical night's sleep cycling through the stages of NREM and REM multiple times. Adapted from [12]

2.1.1 NREM Sleep

NREM sleep is traditionally divided into three stages. Each stage is characterized primarily by the predominant brainwave pattern measured via EEG. During NREM sleep, EEG patterns typically exhibit synchronous activity, characterized by sleep spindles, K-complexes, and high-voltage slow waves. The three stages represent a spectrum of sleep depth, with the first stage (N1) being the lightest and the third stage (N3) the deepest. As such, arousal thresholds are generally lowest during N1 and highest during N3 [11],[13].

N1

The first stage of NREM sleep represents the transition from wakefulness to sleep. During sleep onset, alpha waves (typically ranging from 8 to 12Hz) appear. N1 is considered to have started once more than 50% of the alpha waves have been replaced with low-amplitude mixed-frequency (LAMF) activity such as theta waves (4-8 Hz). Lasting around 5 to 7 minutes, this stage comprises roughly 5% of total sleep time [13].

N2

The second stage of NREM indicates slightly deeper sleep which requires more intense stimuli to be disrupted. The start of this stage is characterized by the presence of two EEG waveforms: sleep spindles and K-complexes. Sleep spindles are short bursts of neuronal activity with a frequency typically ranging from 11 to 16 Hz (**Figure 2**). Numerous studies suggest they play a role in memory consolidation, particularly for procedural and declarative memory [13] [14]. K-complexes are long delta waves (0.5-4 Hz) that occur in response to both internal and external stimuli. They are thought to play a role in maintaining sleep by suppressing arousal as well as memory consolidation. N2 typically lasts around 25 minutes in the first sleep cycle and lengthens with each successive cycle, comprising about 45% of overall sleep [13] [15].

N3

N3, also referred to as slow-wave-sleep (SWS), is considered to be the deepest stage of sleep. Like K-complexes during N2, N3 is characterized by delta waves. Despite having similar frequency ranges, delta waves during SWS are identifiable by their smooth waveform as opposed to K-complexes which have a more complex waveform consisting of a sharp, high amplitude negative component followed by a slow positive component (**Figure 2**). With the highest arousal threshold, an incrementally larger stimulus is required to disrupt sleep at this stage. Sleep disruption during N3 can lead to a prolonged period of mental foginess after waking referred to as sleep inertia. Slow-wave-sleep periods can last from 20 to 40 minutes, making up 25% of total sleep [13].

2.1.2 REM Sleep

REM sleep is a unique stage primarily characterized and distinguished by the occurrence of rapid eye movements. Though muscle movement is inhibited, this stage is not considered to be restful as EEG activity appears similar to an awake individual. This stage typically starts 90 minutes into the first sleep cycle and increases in

Figure 2: Adapted from [16].

length with each subsequent cycle. The first REM cycle typically lasts 10 minutes, while the final cycle may last up to 1 hour. Most vivid dreaming occurs in humans during REM sleep which comprises roughly 25% of total sleep [9] [13].

2.1.3 Biological Rhythm and Sleep Cycles

Biological rhythms refer to periodic fluctuations in an organism’s physiological functions that synchronize with both environmental changes and internal biological processes. These rhythms serve as internal clocks coordinating various bodily functions and activities, allowing organisms to adapt to their environments, and promoting overall health and functioning [17]. Located in the brain, above the optic nerves, this master clock known as the Suprachiasmatic Nucleus (SCN), comprises thousands of nerve cells. The cycles can be regulated internally via the nervous system and externally in response to environmental factors such as the time of day, geographic location, food ingestion, drugs and medications, or moon phases. Different rhythms are categorized based on their duration and underlying mechanisms. Hu-

man biorhythms are split into three cycles based on duration [17] [18]:

Ultradian: cycles lasting less than 24 hours

Circadian: cycles lasting approximately 24 hours

Infradian: cycles lasting more than 24 hours

Within humans, cycles of wakefulness and sleep follow a circadian rhythm lasting roughly 24 hours. While the internal clock regulates this cycle, it synchronizes with the 24-hour pattern of light and darkness. Within the sleep portion of this cycle exists an ultradian cycle between NREM and REM sleep. The body completes approximately 4 to 6 of these cycles per night, each lasting 90 to 110 minutes on average [13].

2.1.4 Napping

Sleep Phases

Understanding the nuances of sleep patterns is integral to comprehending human sleep behavior and its impact on cognitive and physiological functions. Not only is sleep categorized into distinct stages, but also into broader patterns such as monophasic, biphasic, and polyphasic sleep schedules. Monophasic sleep involves a single, consolidated bout of nightly rest, while biphasic sleep incorporates a shorter period of nighttime sleep supplemented by a daytime nap. Polyphasic sleep entails multiple short sleep episodes spread throughout the day. Within this landscape of diverse sleep patterns, beliefs vary regarding the most effective sleep schedule for maximizing alertness, productivity, and overall well-being [14].

Many animals meet their daily sleep needs by taking intermittent naps, making them polyphasic sleepers. While some proponents claim increased productivity and creativity in humans, scientific evidence is scant and mostly negative. A literature review conducted by the National Sleep Foundation [19] found only 22 studies on polyphasic sleep from 1935 to 2020. The review concluded that polyphasic sleep schedules are detrimental to physical health, mental health, and cognitive perfor-

mance.

The debate between monophasic and biphasic sleep patterns continues, with conflicting evidence and interpretations challenging the notion of a default state for human sleep. Biphasic sleep patterns comprised of a long sleep duration (6-7 hours) at night with a short nap during the day (≤ 1 hour) are the prevailing norm in many Mediterranean and Latin American countries [20]. A literature review conducted by researchers Lovato and Lack [21] found the benefits of napping include:

- The ability to catch up on sleep after sleep deprivation
- Improved cognitive abilities
- Increases in physical and mental performance
- Decreases in safety risks associated with sleep deprivation
- Reduction of stress
- Mood improvements
- Increased productivity
- Reduced risk of health conditions associated with sleep loss

Critics of biphasic sleep patterns present compelling evidence suggesting a potential link between daytime napping and adverse health outcomes. Numerous studies, including those by Li et al. [22], demonstrating an increased risk of depression, Liu et al. [23], indicating a higher risk of diabetes, and Yamada et al. [24], identifying a heightened risk of cardiovascular disease, underscore the concerning associations with daytime napping and its impact on overall health.

However, proponents of biphasic sleep argue that these studies may not fully account for the cultural and individual variations in sleep patterns. Studies such as Naska et al. [25] indicate that there is no significant increase in mortality or adverse cardiovascular events in healthy individuals. Furthermore, the methodological limitations

of some studies, such as inadequate control for confounding factors like pre-existing health conditions or variations in nap duration and frequency, cast doubt on the generalizability of their findings.

Power Napping

Power napping, defined as a brief period of sleep lasting typically between 10 to 20 minutes, has been shown to offer significant cognitive and physiological benefits. Studies suggest that even short naps can counteract the effects of sleep deprivation by reducing the accumulation of adenosine in the brain, a chemical that promotes sleepiness [26]. Moreover, naps have been linked to improved mood, increased alertness, and better performance in tasks requiring sustained attention. For example, a systematic review [27] found that short daytime naps, especially those taken in the early afternoon, significantly enhance alertness and cognitive function, making them a potentially valuable tool for improving productivity and well-being in various settings

Sleep Inertia

Sleep inertia, the grogginess and impaired cognitive function experienced upon waking from a nap, further complicates the discourse surrounding the benefits of napping. This phenomenon is characterized by a temporary period of reduced alertness and performance immediately after waking. Hilditch et al. [3] suggest the negative effects of sleep inertia normally wear off within 30 minutes of awakening, however, other researchers [28] suggest effects may last up to 3.5 hours. The detrimental effects of sleep inertia include decreased cognitive functioning, impaired memory consolidation, reduced reaction time, and diminished vigilance, all of which can hinder productivity and performance in daily activities. Moreover, the potential risks associated with sleep inertia extend beyond cognitive domains, including compromised motor coordination and increased susceptibility to accidents and errors [3, 29]. As such, while napping may offer temporary respite from sleep deprivation and promote alertness and performance in the short term, the negative consequences of sleep inertia underscore the need for careful consideration and strategic planning of nap

timing and duration to mitigate its impact on overall well-being and functioning.

It is often assumed that the most effective way to reduce the negative effects of napping is to take short daytime naps (conventionally referred to as power napping). The National Sleep Foundation recommends naps between 20 and 30 minutes to prevent disruptions to nighttime sleep and avoid sleep inertia [30]. Perhaps the most frequently cited rationale for this recommendation comes from Dinges et al.'s study of the relationship between sleep depth and sleep inertia. Their study [31] measured participants' reaction time after being woken up from different stages of sleep, finding that the most severe reduction in performance as compared to a no-sleep control group occurred in participants woken up during N3.

A more recent review conducted by Hilditch et al. [32] investigated the relationship between short naps and sleep inertia. The review found that although SWS is thought to occur 30 minutes after sleep onset normally, it may appear in naps lasting only 10-15 minutes. Additionally, the reviewed literature did not support a direct association between SWS and sleep inertia during short naps. Hilditch et al. instead suggest that controlling nap length rather than sleep stage may be a more appropriate way to reduce negative effects. Researchers concluded that under well-rested conditions, daytime naps of 20 minutes appear to have the best cost/benefit trade-off. The same is true of 10-minute daytime naps under moderate sleep loss conditions (≤ 5 hours total sleep time during the previous night) [32].

2.2 Sound and Sleep

As our understanding deepens regarding the connection between the sleeping brain and external stimuli, researchers are increasingly motivated to bridge this gap. Observations indicating that auditory stimuli elicit EEG responses in the sleeping brain have sparked investigations into the effects of sound on sleep patterns [33]. Insufficient sleep, difficulty falling asleep, and poor sleep quality are widely acknowledged concerns. Audio intervention emerges as a promising tool due to its non-invasive, non-pharmaceutical, cost-effective, and user-friendly nature, making it a viable and

appealing option for enhancing sleep outcomes.

The way in which sound is perceived may vary throughout the sleep cycle. Using a combination of EEG, heart rate monitoring, and functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI) Wilf et al. [34] were able to demonstrate that during NREM sleep the brain exhibits higher selectivity towards sounds, reducing the likelihood of arousal compared to wakefulness or REM sleep. During this stage the brain filters out extraneous noises, prioritizing responses to salient or meaningful stimuli such as an alarm clock or crying infant. This difference in sound perception is partly due to the reduced activity in the thalamus, a brain region responsible for relaying sensory information to the cortex, which diminishes the processing of non-relevant auditory stimuli during NREM sleep [35]. In contrast, during REM sleep, the thalamus becomes more active, allowing more sensory input to reach the cortex, thereby making the brain more responsive to external auditory stimuli. As a result, certain sounds may influence dream content during this stage, as researchers have concluded [36]. The increased cortical activation during REM sleep also reflects the brain's heightened state of internal processing, which may contribute to the vividness of dreams during this phase [35].

Continual progress to better understand how sound is perceived during sleep has paved the way for a growing body of research on how sound can be utilized to improve sleep. The following sections review different types of auditory interventions, including music, non-musical sounds, and targeted entrainment techniques, examining their specific effects on various stages of sleep.

2.2.1 Music and Sleep

Numerous studies have investigated the positive impact of music on sleep in both healthy individuals [37, 38] and those with sleep-disrupting conditions [39, 40, 41] aiming to provide robust evidence for its efficacy. For instance, studies investigating music as a possible treatment for insomnia have found that listening to relaxing

music before bed was among the most powerful interventions for primary insomnia¹ [39, 40].

Despite extensive research on music's relationship with sleep, consensus remains elusive within the scientific community regarding which types of music are most beneficial for sleep and the underlying mechanisms. A meta-analysis of music and sleep-related studies [42] aimed to summarize the function music holds in aiding sleep. From 15 peer-reviewed studies, six reasons were identified:

- Music can encourage relaxation which may lead to sleep
- Music can have positive impacts on mood which can facilitate sleep
- Music can distract the listener from focusing on stressful thoughts that may otherwise interrupt sleep
- Low-frequency neural activity present during sleep can be induced from auditory information at similar frequencies (a phenomenon referred to as entrainment (see next subsection))
- Music may drown out or minimize otherwise problematic external background noise
- Music believed to be helpful in aiding sleep could induce a placebo effect in the listener

Other research [43, 44] aimed to identify what musical features aid sleep. Through feature extraction and analysis of songs identified by survey respondents as having been successfully used to aid sleep, it was revealed that effective sleep music is most commonly comprised of mid-range frequencies, with medium tempos, and in major keys.

¹Primary insomnia is a sleep disorder characterized by difficulty falling or staying asleep without an identifiable underlying cause.

²Secondary insomnia is difficulty sleeping that occurs as a symptom of an underlying medical, psychiatric, or environmental condition.

Importantly, many studies finding music to aid sleep are limited to significant findings only when considering subjective measures whether objective measurement was considered or not. Researchers Chang et al. [45] did not observe any positive effects of music playing on objective measures of sleep onset, total sleep time or sleep efficiency despite observing positive effects when measuring subjective sleep quality.

While less common, a growing body of research has begun to explore the objective effects of music on sleep parameters, shedding light on its tangible benefits beyond mere perceptions of sleep quality. Through EEG monitoring during sound-based sleep interventions, researchers have identified music that has the ability to increase the amount of slow-wave sleep [46, 15], reduce sleep onset time [47], and reduce the amount of time spent in N1 [38].

2.2.2 **Entrainment**

Entrainment, the synchronization of external stimuli, such as music or sound, with internal rhythms, offers promising avenues for enhancing sleep quality and inducing relaxation. Studies have explored various methods of entrainment to investigate their effects on sleep quality. For instance, music compositions featuring auditory pulsing within specific frequency ranges, such as 0.25–2 Hz [48] and 0.25 Hz to 4 Hz [41], have demonstrated potential in improving subjective sleep quality in individuals both with and without sleep disorders. While these interventions may not significantly alter sleep architecture, they have shown promise in reducing sleep onset latency and enhancing perceived sleep quality. Additionally, techniques like audio brain entrainment, which combines alpha (9-12 Hz) and theta frequencies (4-8 Hz), aim to induce changes in brainwave patterns to facilitate relaxation and sleep initiation [40]. Moreover, studies exploring the efficacy of binaural beat stimulation have highlighted its potential to minimize the time required to fall asleep compared to other auditory stimuli such as pure tones without beats [49]. Overall, entrainment techniques present intriguing possibilities for leveraging music and sound to improve subjective sleep quality and enhance overall well-being.

2.2.3 Non-musical Sound and Sleep

Other types of non-musical auditory interventions have demonstrated efficacy in promoting sleep onset and continuity. Several studies have explored the effects of continuous noise, particularly white noise, on sleep initiation and maintenance. A systematic review [6] synthesized evidence on the impact of continuous noise throughout the sleep finding it to be generally beneficial, possibly due to its ability to mask disruptive sounds. The review examined the effects of continuous noise on sleep onset latency, reporting reductions in various populations, including infants, children, college students, adults, and patients. Although statistical significance was not consistently achieved across age populations, these findings suggest a trend toward improved sleep initiation with continuous noise exposure. Moreover, experimental models of transient insomnia [5] have demonstrated the efficacy of broadband sound administration in reducing sleep onset latency by a significant margin compared to normal environmental noise. Evidence supporting noise as a sleep aid across these various studies is reinforced by the incorporation of both subjective and objective measures in its assessment.

Researchers Yeo et al. [50] characterize white and pink noise as continuous and repetitive, noting that many sounds existing in nature share these acoustic features. In their 2015 study, forest noises with similar acoustic profiles to pink noise such as birds chirping and water flowing were comparatively analyzed finding significant similarities in the spectral content. However, it's important to note that the researchers did not conduct a sleep experiment using these natural sounds. Empirical evidence in support of nature sounds as a sleep intervention was provided by researchers investigating the effect of nature sounds on sleep quality in patients hospitalized in cardiac care units [51]. Patients in the experimental group were provided headphones and listened either to nature sounds or wore the headphones without any sounds playing. Compared to a control group which had no sound intervention, both the nature sounds and silence groups showed significant improvements in sleep quality, though there was no difference between the two sound interventions. Both sound interventions were likely successful due to their masking of environmental

noises that would otherwise inhibit sleep, however further research is needed to determine if the sonic qualities of nature sounds are more effective than other sound interventions.

Within the conversation of sound as a potential sleep aid, it is critical to consider the negative effects of sound on sleep. The World Health Organization (WHO) has defined the sound level inside bedrooms to 45 dB, outside 60 dB as the lowest critical value with the potential to produce adverse health effects such as sleep disturbances [38]. Interestingly, Frei et al. [52] demonstrated that noise exposure is not necessarily a mediating factor of perceived sleep quality. The study used both subjective and objective measures to assess sleep quality during exposure to traffic noise. Researchers found that traffic noise objectively decreased sleep quality, but self-reported sleep quality is mediated by noise annoyance.

2.2.4 Stage specific sleep enhancement

To understand in more detail the role of sound in sleep, a growing body of research has formed examining the effects of auditory interventions on specific sleep stages. The majority of findings in this area of work are related to sleep onset as many health conditions have a negative effect on sleep onset latency (SOL), while a growing body of research examines sound's relation to phenomena that occur during N2 such as sleep spindles.

Sleep Onset

Research into the effects of acoustic stimulation on sleep onset has yielded varied findings. Studies from Gao et al. [47] and Chen et al. [53] suggest positive impacts on sleep latency and deep sleep duration through slow-wave brain music and sedative music, two types of music intentionally composed and selected based on their potential to assist in relaxation and induce sleep. Similarly, a study [54] exposing subjects to an 800 Hz tone at 70 dB in a 2-second on, 2-second off interval demonstrated significant efficacy in reducing SOL. Researchers Ho et al. [40] were able to synchronize brainwave frequency with pulse tones emitted by a pillow integrated

with audio speakers with initial results showing a positive effect on SOL.

N1

Very few studies have examined the possibility of improving sleep during N1 via auditory intervention. This may be due to the fact that there are no known cognitive benefits during N1. Instead it is viewed as a short transitory stage which marks sleep onset. Auditory intervention studies that differentiate results by stage have suggested that relaxing music [38], entrainment using pulse tones at alpha (9-12 Hz) and theta (4-8 Hz) frequencies [40], and exposure to pure tone stimuli [55] all have the potential to decrease the total time spent in N1. Spending less time in the N1 stage of NREM may be beneficial as it would proportionally increase the amount of time spent in deeper NREM stages which play important roles in physical and mental maintenance.

N2

During N2 sleep, the effects of sound interventions on sleep spindles have garnered significant interest, offering insights into memory consolidation mechanisms. Choi et al. [56] highlights the neurophysiological effects of acoustic stimulation after spindle activity detection. The study observed phase-locked slow oscillations (SO), delta, and theta activities in response to acoustic stimuli following sleep spindle detection. Notably, the study suggests that acoustic stimulation should be delivered after spindle activity diminishes to evoke SO activity effectively, indicating the importance of timing in eliciting desired neurophysiological responses. Furthermore, the discussion elucidates the association between spindle-SO pairs and motor memory enhancement, emphasizing the significance of individualized stimulation parameters in optimizing memory consolidation. Conversely, Antony and Paller, 2017 [4] explores the frequency-specific manipulation of sleep spindles through acoustic resonance. The study demonstrates the ability to selectively modulate slow and fast spindles using oscillating white noise bursts whose amplitudes modulate at the same frequency as the two spindle types, providing new insights into spindle subtyping and external influences on spindle dynamics. Moreover, the discussion underscores

the potential of spindle manipulation methods to shed light on the role of spindles in cognitive function and offers avenues for further research into mechanisms of spindle generation and potential applications in populations with aberrant spindle activity.

2.3 Sleep Monitoring and Sound Integration

This section explores the methodologies and technologies employed in monitoring sleep stages and integrating sound for sleep enhancement. We explore traditional methods of sleep monitoring, examining their advantages and limitations. Additionally, we review existing systems and tools utilized for sleep scoring and differences in real-time versus offline settings. Furthermore, we explore the potential of sound generation platforms for creating customized audio interventions to enhance sleep quality. Finally, we discuss previous efforts to integrate physiological monitoring with sound generation systems, addressing challenges and opportunities in designing effective interventions tailored to individual sleep patterns.

2.3.1 Methods to Monitor Sleep

With the acknowledged significance of quality sleep and the widespread issue of insufficient rest, sleep monitoring has emerged as a pivotal realm of research. Effective sleep monitoring systems can sense physiological changes, process the observed parameters, and output relevant information regarding sleep stages, sleep disorders, posture, or vital signs. Clinical methods, conducted in controlled environments with the supervision of trained staff currently have the highest accuracy and as such are considered as standards for sleep monitoring. These techniques are considered to be invasive as they involve various types and combinations of sensors attached to different body parts. The sensors may cause sleep disturbance and are not considered viable for long-term monitoring [57].

Electroencephalography

The electroencephalogram (EEG) is the most widely used tool in sleep research. This neurophysiological monitoring technique is used to record the electrical activity

of the brain. It involves placing electrodes on the scalp to detect and measure electrical signals detected by brain activity. EEG monitoring has high levels of temporal resolution allowing researchers to capture rapid changes in brain activity with millisecond precision. However, it has poor spatial resolution compared to other monitoring techniques making it difficult to precisely localize the source of brain activity [58].

Electrocardiography

Electrocardiography (ECG) is a measure of the electrical activity of the heart over a period of time using electrodes placed on the skin, providing valuable information about the heart's rhythm. This allows for the detection of disordered breathing and cardiovascular abnormality assessments, however does not provide comprehensive information about other aspects of sleep such as brain activity or respiratory function [59].

Electromyography

Electromyography (EMG) is a diagnostic technique used to evaluate the electrical activity produced by skeletal muscles. This technique is considered essential for defining REM sleep and for quantifying some types of movements in sleep, such as periodic limb movements (PLM) or teeth grinding. This technique is highly sensitive to changes in muscle activity, however as such may be susceptible to artifacts from electrode displacement [60].

Electrooculography

Electrooculography (EOG) is a technique used to measure the electrical activity of muscles surrounding the eyes. In sleep monitoring, EOG is commonly employed to detect eye movements indicative of sleep stage changes and REM detection. While this measurement technique is highly sensitive to changes in eye movement, it does not provide comprehensive information about other aspects of sleep architecture or physiology [61].

Polysomnography

Polysomnography (PSG) is considered to be the current gold standard technique for sleep analysis [62]. Data from EEG, EOG, EMG, and ECG monitoring is combined with measures of nasal airflow and pulse oximetry to provide the most comprehensive overview of sleep possible. While PSG may be the most effective way to observe sleep and its various disorders, it is an expensive and complex process that requires patients to wear various sensors, and is not suitable for long-term observation or at-home use [63].

Actigraphy

Actigraphy is a relatively non-invasive approach gaining popularity in health care solutions. In this approach, a device consisting of an accelerator is attached to the wrist or ankle of a subject and used to record physical movements through the sleep period. This technique may be advantageous in situations where it is important to measure sleep-wake cycles over long periods of time, but it only provides information about the wake-sleep activity and physical movements during sleep [64].

Cognitive Performance Measures

Beyond physiological measures of sleep, objective sleep quality may also be measured indirectly by observing changes in cognitive performance. Cognitive performance tests, particularly those assessing memory and attention, evaluate the impact of sleep quality and duration on cognitive functioning. Studies have demonstrated that sleep deprivation impairs cognitive performance across various domains, with memory being especially susceptible. For example, Yoo et al. found that sleep-deprived participants exhibited reduced activity in the hippocampus, a brain region crucial for memory formation, during memory encoding tasks, resulting in significantly poorer performance on subsequent recall tests [65]. Similarly, Van Dongen et al. utilized the Psychomotor Vigilance Task (PVT)³ and observed that cognitive performance, including reaction time and lapses of attention, declined progressively with sleep

³<https://shorturl.at/nFLu9>

restriction [66]. In another study, Drummond et al. examined working memory using the N-back task, where participants must determine if the current stimulus matches the one shown 'n' trials ago. Researchers found significant declines in performance after one night of total sleep deprivation, highlighting the sensitivity of working memory to sleep loss [67].

2.3.2 Subjective Measurement of Sleep

While subjective measurements of sleep do not provide the level of detail or accuracy that clinical measures may provide, they are an important consideration in the sleep research as they can highlight discrepancies between clinically recorded and subject-perceived sleep quality. Among the most widely used subjective methods is the sleep diary. A sleep diary requires the subject to record daily estimates of relevant sleep parameters from the prior nights sleep [68]. The success of a sleep diary relies heavily on prospective recordings taken immediately after waking which may be difficult for subjects to consistently remember to complete [69]. In contrast, self-report questionnaires such as the Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index (PSQI), offer straightforward, low-cost measurements of the same parameters that have been found to have higher levels of subject compliance [69, 70].

2.3.3 Sleep Quality Analysis

The term sleep quality is used to refer to many specific parameters of sleep possible to be measured via both subjective and objective measurements. The most common measures are [71, 72]:

- Total Sleep Time (TST): the total duration of sleep during a specific time period, typically measured in hours
- Sleep Onset Latency (SOL): The amount of time it takes to fall asleep after going to bed, usually measured in minutes
- Sleep maintenance: The ability to stay asleep throughout the night without frequent awakenings or disruptions

- Wakefulness After Sleep Onset (WASO): The total amount of time spent awake after initially falling asleep and before final awakening in the morning, typically measured in minutes.
- Total Wake Time (TWT): The cumulative duration of wakefulness during the sleep period, including both sleep onset latency and wakefulness after sleep onset, typically measured in minutes.
- Sleep Efficiency (SE): The ratio of total sleep time to the total time spent in bed, expressed as a percentage, indicating how efficiently sleep time is utilized during the sleep period.

Important observations leading to the objective measurement of the above sleep quality indicators can be achieved by extracting sleep cycle information from electrophysiological signals. This process, known as sleep scoring, relies on EEG, EOG, and/or EMG to compare sleep stages, arousal, respiratory events, movements, and cardiac events [73]. The procedure for this evaluation technique was standardized worldwide in 2007 when the AASM published a scoring manual [74]. While this historically was a tedious and time-consuming process that involved hours of manually searching for visual indicators in electrophysiological data records, advances in deep learning have paved the way for a market of automatic sleep scoring products that perform with high accuracy. [75, 76].

While the majority of these algorithms only work offline, a growing body of research aims to develop real-time automatic sleep-scoring techniques as well. For example, Esfahani et al. [77] introduced Dreamento, an open-source Python package for sleep engineering using EEG wearables. Among other capabilities, Dreamento offers a free-to-use technology for automatic sleep scoring which holds significant relevancy in the field of auditory stimulation during sleep.

2.3.4 Design and Implementation Considerations

A well-designed system for sleep monitoring during sound-based interventions should take into account both the importance of accurate data collection as well as the needs

of the subject. When using clinical sleep evaluation tools it is important to control as many variables as possible in the test setting, such as temperature, light levels, and external sound. Additionally, a reliable sound generation system is necessary to allow researchers to have complete control over sonic parameters.

Max/MSP is a powerful visual programming language designed for creating interactive music and multimedia applications. With its intuitive graphical interface, users can design and manipulate audio signals, MIDI data, and video in real time, allowing for the creation of dynamic and responsive soundscapes [78]. In the context of sound-based sleep interventions, Max/MSP offers several advantages. Firstly, it provides a flexible platform for generating and controlling the various types of sounds used in sleep interventions, including pure tones, sedative music, nature sounds, and binaural beats. Max/MSP's real-time capabilities enable the integration of physiological data, such as EEG signals, allowing for adaptive sound generation based on the user's electrophysiological output. Additionally, Max/MSP's ability to interface with external devices and sensors facilitates the development of sleep-intervention systems that can respond dynamically to changes in the sleep environment or the user's physiological parameters [79, 80].

When designing a music-based sleep intervention, it is crucial to consider the diverse needs and preferences of the subjects involved. Both for the user's comfort, and the maintenance of an environment conducive to healthy sleep, as few sensors and devices as possible should be employed while ensuring that sufficient data can be collected. One such device, the Hypnodyne ZMax, presents a wearable PSG system in the form of a headband. This system which incorporates both EEG and EMG monitoring, shows significant success as an accurate and relatively non-invasive system when compared with other more robust PSG systems [81].

2.4 Current Study

This State of the Art has highlighted the growing interest in using auditory stimuli to enhance sleep quality, with particular attention to non-musical sounds such as

white noise. While existing research has established the efficacy of white noise in promoting sleep onset and maintenance, most studies have focused on its use as a masking tool against environmental noise rather than as a sleep enhancement strategy. This leaves a notable gap in understanding white noise's direct influence on sleep architecture, including its potential to improve overall sleep quality.

Paller and Antony's 2017 study [4] investigated the manipulation of sleep spindles using oscillating white noise, however the investigation concentrated only on its effects over daytime naps lasting 120 minutes. Furthermore, this study primarily found that sleep spindle density increases in the presence of oscillating white noise in lateral brain regions, but did not provide convincing evidence that the same effect was achieved in frontal regions. There remains a lack of research examining the impact of such auditory interventions on shorter sleep periods, with a specific focus on frontal regions.

To address these gaps in the literature, this thesis asks the following research question:

Can audio stimulation before and during the early stages of sleep improve sleep onset latency and increase spindle density during short daytime naps?

The current study aims to investigate the impact of auditory stimuli on sleep onset latency and sleep quality during short naps by adapting a similar procedure to Antony & Paller, 2017. Specifically, two hypotheses will be tested: **(1) unmodulated pink noise will decrease sleep onset latency, and (2) amplitude-modulated pink noise will increase sleep spindle density.**

Chapter 3

Methods

This section details the methodology and materials used to investigate the effects of auditory stimuli on sleep quality and memory consolidation. Brain activity was monitored using a specialized EEG headband, while pink noise and modulated pink noise were generated through a controlled audio system. Participants completed a memory task before and after napping to assess the effects of these sounds on memory consolidation. Sleep quality was also measured using a self-report questionnaire. The study's design allowed for a direct comparison of sleep quality across different sound conditions, with data analyzed to explore the relationship between auditory stimuli and sleep during brief naps.

3.1 Subjects

10 subjects were screened via an anonymous online questionnaire to ensure all participants met the following inclusion and exclusion criteria:

Inclusion Criteria

1. Age 18-45 years
2. Generally healthy with no chronic conditions affecting sleep
3. Regular sleep habits, getting 7-9 hours of sleep per night generally

Exclusion Criteria

1. No history of sleep disorders
2. No history of neurological issues
3. Not currently taking any medications that could influence sleep or cognitive function
4. No hearing issues or impairments
5. No recent history of substance abuse or dependence

The inclusion and exclusion criteria were selected to ensure a consistent and healthy sample. The criteria reduce the likelihood that any confounding variable affecting sleep will skew the data allowing for more reliable and valid results.

Of $N = 10$ screened subjects, 4 did not meet the inclusion criteria. Due to technical problems and the failure to fall asleep during experimentation, data was not included for two participants. The final analyses were conducted on a sample size of $N = 4$ subjects (1 male, 3 female, aged 23-26 years).

3.2 Materials

3.2.1 Sleep Recording

In order to capture the brain signals, a 3-electrode headband called Hypnodyne ZMax¹ was used. The ZMax headband comprises two frontal EEG channels, a tri-axial accelerometer, and a photoplethysmography (PPG) sensor, all with a sampling frequency of 256 Hz. The ZMax device sends the brain signals to a PC via a wireless connection using a proprietary protocol, which ensures a steady latency of 3.5 milliseconds. This device was selected for its well-established accuracy and participant comfort in prior sleep studies, demonstrating its reliability in sleep research

¹<https://hypnodynecorp.com/index.php>

[81]. Captured brain signals were monitored and analyzed using HDRecorder, a proprietary signal acquisition tool also developed by Hypnodyne.

3.2.2 Sound Generation

All sounds used throughout the test sessions were generated using Max/MSP [78], a visual programming environment for music and audio signal processing. Sound was controlled via a custom-built interface which also allowed for the recording of important sleep events that occurred throughout test sessions (Figure 3).

Figure 3: This custom built Max/MSP patch allowed for the generation of auditory stimuli and recording of relevant time-based events throughout the test sessions.

3.3 Experiment proceedings

3.3.1 Stimuli

Participants, depending on the current intervention and sleep stage, were exposed to one of three sound conditions: silence, unmodulated pink noise or amplitude-modulated pink noise. Both the unmodulated and modulated pink noise stimuli were generated using the 'pink~' object in Max/MSP. The 'pink~' object generates a signal consisting of random values in the range -1.0 to 1.0, with an even distribution of power per octave of frequency.

The modulated pink noise alternated between 100% and 20% of its original amplitude in the form of a sine wave. Modulations at 12 Hz occurred during the first 2 seconds of a 10-second pink noise signal, such that each 2-second period of modulated pink noise was followed by 8 seconds of unmodulated pink noise (**Figure 4**). The modulation frequency was set to the same frequency of sleep spindles that occur in the brain's frontal regions measured by the ZMax device, in line with the proceedings of [4]. The stimulation protocol used in [4] also modulated between 100% and 20% of the original amplitude at a frequency of 12Hz, but white noise was used for this study rather than pink noise.

Figure 4: A waveform representation of the repeated stimuli heard during the N2 phase of test

3.3.2 Experiment design

A repeated measures design was employed such that each participant completed two test sessions: an experimental session and a control session. Subjects completed

each session on consecutive afternoons, each occurring at the same time on both days between 13:00 and 17:00. To counterbalance the order of conditions, participants were randomly assigned to start with one of the two sessions, ensuring that any potential order effects were evenly distributed across the conditions.

In the experimental condition, participants were exposed to unmodulated pink noise during the period from wake until N2. Once participants reached sleep stage N2, the noise was switched to amplitude-modulated pink noise. A 15-minute timer was then started to prevent participants from continuing to deeper stages of sleep.

In the control condition, participants heard no auditory stimuli (silence) during the period from wake until N2. Once participants reached sleep stage N2 unmodulated pink noise was played. The same 15-minute timer was used in this condition.

Participation in both conditions allowed for a comparative analysis of sleep quality within each subject. EEG data from the pre-N2 stage with no sound was compared to the pre-N2 stage with unmodulated pink noise, and the N2 stage with unmodulated pink noise was compared to the N2 stage with modulated pink noise (**Figure 5**).

Figure 5: Each participant took one nap in each condition. For each participant SOL was compared between the silence and unmodulated pink noise stimuli (blue), while spindle density was compared between the unmodulated pink noise and modulated pink noise stimuli (orange).

Changes in stimuli were manually enforced upon N2 detection by the researcher. To ensure accuracy, the author validated his ability to sleep score correctly using an examination included in Sprigg's Essentials of Polysomnography training guide

for sleep technicians, scoring at 90%, higher than the state-of-the-art for automatic sleep scoring algorithms [8].

3.3.3 Procedure

Participants arrived at the laboratory for a nap lasting anywhere from 15 minutes to one hour. They were asked to refrain from drinking caffeine, alcohol, or consuming tobacco in the morning before the test session, as well as being asked not to eat within two hours of the experiment's start time. After informed consent was obtained and a brief overview of the study was given, each participant was given five minutes to complete the pre-nap encoding phase of the word-pair association task. Each participant was then given an alcohol wipe to sanitize their forehead before being fitted with the ZMax headband. After calibrating the device and confirming that a strong and constant signal was streaming, participants then laid in a bed in a cool, quiet, and dark room to try to fall asleep (**Figure 6**). The loudness level of the auditory stimuli was measured before each test session to ensure that the total loudness level in the room did not exceed 50dB SPL. During the nap portion of the test session, the experimenter continuously monitored EEG recordings from an adjacent room to determine the current sleep stage and administer the appropriate stimuli depending on the condition. If a participant was unable to fall asleep, the sleep session was ended after 60 minutes. After awakening, each participant was given 5 minutes to prepare themselves before completing the post-nap recall phase of the word-pair association task as well as the Leeds Sleep Evaluation Questionnaire. The procedure for the two study sessions completed by each participant was identical aside from the auditory stimuli which were dependent on the current condition, and the content of the memory task.

Figure 6: The sleep lab included a bed and a speaker (located in the bottom left corner)

3.4 Measurements

3.4.1 Polysomnography

EEG data was collected throughout the nap portion of each test session using the ZMax device. The three electrodes were placed on the forehead of each participant, with one centered and the other two on the left and right temples. Data were processed offline in Python using various features from the Dreamento toolbox²(**Figure 7**).

Sleep onset latency was determined by the single-file auto-scoring feature and cross-referenced with the author’s manual scoring. The single-file auto-scoring feature outputs a report of the AASM sleep quality metrics which include sleep onset latency (**Figure 8**).

Sleep spindles were detected using Dreamento’s implementation of the Yet Another Spindle Algorithm (YASA), an open-source Python library for sleep spindle detection [82]. The algorithm operates by first bandpass filtering the EEG signal to

²github.com/dreamento

Figure 7: The analysis dashboard for Dreamoto Toolbox

Figure 8: A sample output of AASM sleep quality metrics

isolate the frequency range characteristic of spindles (11-16 Hz). It then employs a shareholding method based on the root mean square (RMS) amplitude of the filtered signal to detect candidate spindles. These candidates are further isolated by duration (>0.5 seconds) and their characteristics are output and stored as a CSV file (Figure 9).

Figure 9: A sample output of an auto-scored sleep session. The green-highlighted EEG data represents detected sleep spindles

3.4.2 Memory Task Performance

To test memory consolidation, a word-pair association task was used consisting of 15 semantically related word pairs (**Appendix A**). The word pairs were randomly selected from a list of 46 pairs used in prior studies related to sleep and cognitive ability [83, 84]. The test takes place in two phases. During the pre-nap encoding phase participants are required to learn the list of word pairs. Later during the post-nap recall phase participants must recall one of the words in each pair when presented with the other. If a participant's native language was Spanish or Catalan a translated version of the test was provided.

3.4.3 Subjective Sleep Quality

In order to measure changes in perceived sleep quality the Leeds Sleep Evaluation Questionnaire was used. The 10-item, subjective, self-report measure (**Appendix B**), was designed to assess changes in sleep quality over the course of a treatment intervention. The scale evaluates four domains: ease of initiating sleep, quality of sleep, ease of waking, and behavior following wakefulness [85].

3.5 Statistical Analyses

With a small sample size ($N = 4$), it cannot be assumed that the difference in measures between participants is normally distributed. As such, a Wilcoxon signed-rank test was used to determine the statistical significance of the findings. The Wilcoxon signed-rank test is a non-parametric statistical test that is used to compare two related samples or matched pairs. It assesses whether the median of the differences between paired observations is significantly different from zero, making it suitable for small sample sizes and data that do not meet the assumptions of normality. The test was conducted using the SciPy library in Python [86], with an alpha level of 0.05.

Chapter 4

Results

The present study examined the impact of auditory stimuli, specifically unmodulated and modulated pink noise, on sleep onset latency, spindle density, memory consolidation, and subjective sleep quality during short naps. The study employed a repeated measures design, where each participant underwent two test sessions: an experimental session with unmodulated pink noise played from wake until the N2 stage, and modulated pink noise beginning at the detection of N2, and a control session with silence until N2 and unmodulated pink noise beginning at the detection of N2. The primary hypotheses were that unmodulated pink noise would decrease sleep onset latency and that modulated pink noise would increase sleep spindle density. Sleep quality and memory performance were also assessed to explore the broader effects of these auditory conditions on cognitive and subjective outcomes.

4.1 Objective Measures

4.1.1 Sleep Onset Latency

Three of the four participants showed a decrease in sleep onset latency while falling asleep in the experimental condition while one participant showed an increase. Results indicate a decrease in sleep onset latency while in the presence of unmodulated pink noise ($M = 844.25$ seconds, $SD = 243.5$ seconds) as compared to silence ($M =$

1252.5 seconds, $SD = 894.33$ seconds). However, the results indicated no significant difference in sleep onset latency between the silence condition and the unmodulated pink noise condition, $W = 2.0$, $p = 0.375$ (Figure 10).

Figure 10: This chart shows the difference in sleep onset latency between the experimental and control conditions (measured in seconds). Negative values indicate that the participant took less time to fall asleep in the experimental condition in the presence of unmodulated pink noise.

4.1.2 Sleep Spindle Density

Out of the 4 participants, 3 showed an increase in sleep spindle density in the presence of modulated pink noise during the experimental condition, while one experienced an increase in the presence of unmodulated pink noise during the control condition. The results indicated no significant difference in spindle density between the unmodulated pink noise condition ($M = 1.83$, $SD = 1.95$) and the modulated pink noise condition ($M = 1.57$, $SD = 1.10$), $W = 4.0$, $p = 0.875$ (Figure 11).

Figure 11: This chart shows the change in spindle density between the experimental and control conditions. Positive values indicate higher spindle density in the experimental condition in the presence of modulated pink noise.

4.1.3 Memory Task

Participants' cognitive test scores were compared between the control and experimental conditions. Two participants' scores increased by 7% while the other two had no change in the percentage of correct answers. The results indicated no significant difference in cognitive test scores between the control condition in which unmodulated pink noise was played during N2 ($M = 96.5$, $SD = 4.04$) and the experimental condition in which modulated pink noise was played during N2 ($M = 100.0$, $SD = 0.0$), $W = 0.0$, $p = 0.157$ (Figure 12).

Figure 12: This chart shows the difference in test scores for the memory tasks taken during the experimental and control conditions. Positive values indicate an increase in the percentage of total correct answers after the experimental condition in which participants heard both unmodulated and modulated pink noise throughout the test session.

4.2 Subjective Measure of Sleep Quality

Participants' subjective sleep quality, as measured by the Leeds SEQ, was compared between the control (silence + unmodulated pink noise) and experimental (unmodulated pink noise + modulated pink noise) conditions. Two participants' total score increased while the other two had decreases in their total score. The mean Leeds SEQ score for the control condition was 163.38 (SD = 83.77), while the mean score for the experimental condition was 149.17 (SD = 53.85). A Wilcoxon signed-rank test indicated that there was no significant difference in subjective sleep quality between the control condition ($M = 163.38$, $SD = 83.77$) and the experimental condition ($M = 149.17$, $SD = 53.85$), $W = 4.0$, $p = 0.875$. These findings

suggest that the experimental condition does not significantly impact participants' subjective sleep quality as measured by the Leeds SEQ (**Figure 13**).

Figure 13: This chart shows the difference in scores on the Leeds Sleep Evaluation Questionnaire taken after the experimental and control conditions. The highest possible score was 400 points. Positive values indicate increased subjective sleep quality measured after the experimental condition.

Overall, the results of this study suggest observable yet statistically insignificant trends in sleep onset latency, spindle density, memory performance, and subjective sleep quality. The data collected across various measures provide a foundation for understanding the relationship between sound and sleep, contributing to the ongoing research in this area.

Chapter 5

Discussion

5.1 Discussion

This thesis investigated the effects of different auditory interventions on various sleep-related parameters during short daytime naps, including sleep onset latency, sleep spindle density, memory consolidation, and subjective sleep quality. Although the measured parameters did not reach statistical significance, the observed trends suggest that further investigation and refinement of the hypotheses in future studies may be worthwhile.

Three of the four participants experienced a decrease in sleep onset latency while falling asleep to unmodulated pink noise as compared to silence. While not statistically significant, these results suggest that unmodulated pink noise may reduce the amount of time it takes to fall asleep. This observation is noteworthy given that the majority of literature examining the effect of broadband noise on SOL suggests that noise may only be beneficial in masking other unwanted noises present at the time of falling asleep. By testing in a quiet environment, the findings from this thesis point to the possibility that broadband noise may be able to decrease sleep onset latency without the presence of unwanted noise.

Similarly, no significant difference was found in sleep spindle density between the unmodulated pink noise condition and the modulated pink noise condition. How-

ever, sleep spindle density increased for three of the four participants during the modulated pink noise condition, hinting at a potential benefit of modulated noise in enhancing sleep spindle activity. This observation aligns with the findings of [4], which suggest that amplitude-modulated white noise oscillating at the frequency of sleep spindles has the potential to elicit sleep spindles. Antony & Paller's 2017 study looked at daytime nap periods of 120 minutes, while the findings from this thesis suggest the same effect may appear during short daytime naps no longer than 60 minutes.

Participants completed the memory task based on literature that suggests sleep spindles play an important role in memory consolidation. As such, the results from the spindle density measurement and memory consolidation task were expected to trend similarly. While spindle density and memory test scores both increased in the experimental condition, it is important to note that the increase in scores was very small beyond its statistical insignificance. Two participants increased their score from 93% accuracy to 100%, while the other two scored a 100% after both the experimental and control conditions. These findings suggest the memory test may not have been long or challenging enough to accurately measure differences in performance. The test consisted of 15 word-pairs selected from a list of 46 pairs used in a similar sleep study that tested memory consolidation [83]. The word-pair task used in Holz's 2012 study was intentionally created using semantically related word pairs, however, the study did not explain the motivation behind this decision. It is possible that participants performed higher on the memory task due to the semantic similarity between the selected words in each pair. While the perfect scores in the modulated pink noise condition suggest a potential advantage for cognitive performance, the small sample size in addition to issues with the task itself limit the generalizability of this finding.

Subjective sleep quality was included as a parameter to gain insight into general experience in each condition. Participants during both test sessions were exposed to two stimuli depending on the current intervention and their current sleep stage. Without the means to control for potential carryover or order effects of the delivered

stimuli, the Leeds SEQ was given to better understand differences in sleep quality between the two conditions. Two participants experienced an increase in subjective sleep quality during the experimental condition, while the other two experienced an increase relative to the control condition. While these findings do not support the hypotheses they are consistent with past literature. This discrepancy is supported by research [87] showing that objective measures of sleep, such as actigraphy, are often more closely associated with specific cognitive domains, while subjective measures do not consistently relate to performance in any cognitive domain when controlling for objective sleep variables. Moreover, age appears to moderate the relationship between sleep and cognitive function differently depending on whether sleep is assessed subjectively or objectively, highlighting the complexity of interpreting sleep quality across different measures. Another study [88] demonstrated that objective and subjective measures of sleep quality often diverge, especially in older adults. This study, investigating the relationship between these measures in older subjects, found that while there was some correlation between objective metrics (such as polysomnography) and subjective reports under certain conditions, there were notable discrepancies. For example, during habitual sleep times, older adults did not perceive their generally poor sleep quality, suggesting that subjective sleep quality may be more sensitive to day-to-day variations or specific changes in sleep conditions rather than providing an accurate overall reflection of objective sleep quality. However, under forced desynchrony conditions, where participants followed a 20-hour rest-activity schedule that altered their habitual sleep timing, subjective sleep ratings showed a stronger association with objective sleep measures.

5.1.1 Limitations

A key aspect to consider is the study's limitations, particularly in its design. The primary limitation is the small sample size ($N = 4$), which greatly reduces the statistical power and generalizability of the findings. Additionally, the study design did not allow for the testing of all possible combinations of auditory stimuli and nap conditions. Specifically, participants were only exposed to two predetermined sequences of sound conditions (unmodulated pink noise followed by modulated pink

noise, and silence followed by unmodulated pink noise), rather than a fully counterbalanced design that could have included other potential combinations, such as modulated pink noise followed by silence. This constraint may have limited the ability to fully explore the effects of different auditory stimuli combinations on the chosen measurements of sleep quality.

In addition to the limitations related to study design, several factors related to measurement and data collection may have influenced the outcomes. Potential errors in measurement from the EEG device as well as errors in the sleep scoring and spindle detection algorithms may have potentially influenced the outcomes. Moreover, the memory task's brief duration and the use of semantically related word pairs, which might be easier to recall, could have limited its effectiveness in assessing memory consolidation. The subjective nature of the Leeds SEQ scores also introduces potential biases and variability. Participants' perceptions, moods, and expectations can vary widely, affecting their responses and potentially skewing the findings. Differences in how participants interpret the SEQ questions or their prior experiences with pink noise might also contribute to variability. Future research with larger sample sizes and a more complicated memory test conducted by expert sleep scorers could help address these issues and confirm the preliminary findings.

5.2 Conclusions

The present study was motivated by the need to explore non-invasive methods to enhance sleep quality, particularly during short daytime naps, which are increasingly recognized for their role in cognitive function and overall well-being. By utilizing a repeated measures design, this study aimed to investigate whether unmodulated and modulated pink noise could effectively influence sleep onset latency and sleep spindle density—two key factors in achieving restorative sleep. The rationale for focusing on pink noise stems from its ability to create a consistent auditory environment that may mask disruptive sounds and promote relaxation, thereby potentially reducing the time it takes to fall asleep. Additionally, modulated pink noise, which was timed to the brain's natural sleep spindle frequency, was hypothesized to synchronize with

and amplify these spindles, possibly enhancing memory consolidation during sleep.

While the study did not find statistically significant differences between the conditions, the observed trends suggest that unmodulated pink noise could potentially decrease sleep onset latency, while modulated pink noise may increase sleep spindle density leading to greater improvements in cognitive performance upon waking from a short daytime naps. Importantly, these findings could be relevant as they offer evidence supporting a low-barrier method to improve sleep quality during short daytime naps. White noise machines are relatively inexpensive, widely available, and easy to use, making them an accessible option for many individuals seeking to enhance their nap quality¹². Improved nap quality can have significant implications for cognitive function, mood, and overall well-being, particularly in populations that benefit from short naps, such as night-shift workers, students, and those with irregular sleep patterns. These findings contribute to a growing body of research on non-invasive strategies to enhance sleep quality, highlighting the potential of pink noise as an easy-to-implement tool that may benefit a wide range of individuals seeking to optimize their cognitive function and overall well-being through improved nap quality.

¹<https://yogasleep.com/products/hushh>

²<https://noiz.io/>

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Appendix A

Word Pair Association Task

Participants studied the word pairs in part 1 for 5 minutes before their nap

DAY 1 TEST 1 PART 1

EVENT - FESTIVAL

FLAKES - RESCUE

BELIEF - RESTRAINT

RULER - COMMAND

AVENUE - THICKET

STATEMENT - WITNESS

UPRISING - SHIELD

ASSIGNMENT - WORK

TRAIN STATION - STATION

BRIDGE - CURRENT

TREATY - PACT

FACTORY - PRODUCTION

MACHINE - CHAIN

GRAIN - BARLEY

INFECTION - PAIN

5 minutes after waking participants were asked to recall the second word of each pair from part 1 given only the first word

DAY 1 TEST 1 PART 2

BRIDGE _____

UPRISING _____

BELIEF _____

FACTORY _____

AVENUE _____

FLAKES _____

GRAIN _____

EVENT _____

RULER _____

TREATY _____

ASSIGNMENT _____

STATEMENT _____

INFECTION _____

TRAIN STATION _____

MACHINE _____

Appendix B

Leeds Sleep Evaluation Questionnaire

How would you describe the way you currently fall asleep in comparison to usual?

1. More difficult than usual _____ Less difficult than usual
2. Slower than usual _____ More quickly than usual
3. I feel less sleepy than _____ More sleepy than usual
usual

How would you describe the quality of your sleep compared to normal sleep?

4. More restless than usual _____ Calmer than usual
5. More wakeful periods _____ Less wakeful periods than
than usual usual

How would you describe your awakening in comparison to usual?

6. More difficult than usual _____ Easier than usual
7. Longer than usual _____ Shorter than usual

How do you feel when you wake up?

8. Tired _____ Alert

How do you feel now?

9. Tired _____ Alert

How would you describe your balance and co-ordination upon awakening?

10. More disrupted than _____ Less disrupted than usual
usual